

Importance of Women's Education

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Abstracts:

The paper shows how **Educating women** is the fastest way to make real fundamental changes in the world, how Educating women positively impacts the economic, social and health standards and how investing in girls' education benefits society and national development. First and foremost, everyone has the basic right to education, and when we say everyone, we should not forget to include women in this group. Women make up a big portion of society, and it would be to our great loss if they were all illiterate. No of their socioeconomic status—wealthy, poor, young, old, married, single, widowed—all girls and women have the fundamental right to an education. Education is a fundamental right, not a privilege.

Key Words: Importance Of Education, Women Education, Girls Education, Importance Of Women Education.

Introduction:

“Give me an educated mother, and I shall promise you the birth of a civilized, educated nation,” said Napoleon

Being educated gives a woman the abilities, information, and self-assurance she needs to be a better mother, employee, and citizen. A lady with a good education will also work harder and earn more money. Women with more education will marry later in life when they are more mature, select better partners for their lives, and make better fathers for their children. Women who are educated will build strong, healthy families that are capable of taking their place in the world and being active members of their communities. Educated women will hold themselves and others around them to higher standards, inspiring the community as a whole to raise its own standards. Anyone can succeed in life with education, but educating women will, in the long term, benefit their families and society as a whole. In fact, women frequently see larger returns on their educational investments than do men.

Everyone has the right to an equitable education, to start with. However, educated females have access to a much wider range of possibilities and can make informed decisions. Girls' education strengthens families, communities, and economies while also saving lives. Women's education boosts a nation's productivity and supports economic expansion. And research conducted a few years ago that claimed that some countries lose more than \$1 billion year by not educating girls to the same level as boys backed this claim.

Benefits of Female Education

Social advancement: Women's education enables them to address societal challenges and difficulties. Education was advocated as a tool for social advancement by the Kothari commission in 1968. India can achieve its goal of social development by educating women.

Gender equality: Women are a disadvantaged group in society. They are aided in closing the gender gap in society by education. Male students in coeducational schools are also taught to respect females.

Economic productivity: Women's education enables a country to increase its economic standing and boosts its GDP.

Infant humanity declines: Educated women are more aware of their family situations and make better judgements for the family to prevent arguments amongst members. Additionally, women's education lowers India's infant mortality rate.

Higher living standards: A woman's employment opportunities will inevitably grow with education. A woman with a strong education may be able to secure a good career and enjoy a higher level of living.

Importance of Girls Education:

1. Basic Fundamental Right

According to the Right to Education Act of 2009, every Indian girl has a basic right to education. With roughly 48.5% of its population being female, India is the second most populous nation in the world. India is one of the nations with the fastest economic growth, yet our women's literacy percentage is much lower than the average worldwide. To raise the country's literacy rates, the Indian government has passed numerous laws and initiatives as the RTE Act 2008 and NEP 2020.

2. For Equality in Society

Discrimination and inequality always begin at the root. When a boy attends school while his sister stays home because she is a girl, these plants the germ of prejudice in the boy's head. He believes that he is superior just because he is a boy, and he lacks any sound reasoning to support this belief. Boys who participate in education by attending schools and colleges alongside women comprehend the fundamental rights of education and don't grow a

sense of superiority. Therefore, educating both men and women advances the concepts of democracy and equality.

3. For Women's Growth, Independence And Confidence

It is unquestionably true that education fosters independence. We can become self-sufficient in terms of providing services to others and supporting ourselves through education. Women can live independently of their families if they pursue an education and a career. This increases their self-assurance and empowers them to make independent decisions. They become aware of their value and individuality. Therefore, educating women is crucial to helping them become autonomous and self-assured.

4. Economic Growth of Nation

Approximately 50% of the population is made up of women. If they are not educated, a significant portion of the population won't be helping the country thrive, which is a serious issue. Consequently, educating women will aid in a nation's development.

5. Helps in Poverty Eradication

Science has proven that education can alleviate poverty. Along with imparting knowledge, education helps people enhance their social, emotional, cognitive, and communication abilities. The ability to access employment, resources, and skills that enable one to not just survive but also thrive is made possible by education, which is the great equaliser. Because of this, having access to a good education is considered a recognised antidote to poverty. Numerous other problems that might make individuals, families, and even entire communities vulnerable to the cycle of poverty can be resolved with education. And absolutely capable of ending poverty.

Challenges To Women's Education

Despite the fact that all nations have reached the pinnacle of development on all fronts, some nations still face obstacles to women's education because they are poor, have a severe lack of sources of income, are embroiled in a brutal war, or both. Although the causes have changed, the result has not changed. Women's access to education is dwindling with time. Here are some of the major difficulties and obstacles that women's education is currently facing:

Gender Bias

In addition to promoting messages that have an impact on girls' aspirations and perceptions of their social responsibilities, gender bias in schools and classrooms can result in discrepancies in labour market participation and occupational segregation. A child's academic performance and choice of major are negatively impacted when gender stereotypes are communicated through the design of the learning

environment in the classroom and at school, as well as through the behaviour of teachers, staff members, and peers. This is especially true for young women who choose to major in STEM fields.

Poverty

One of the most important factors in determining whether a girl can access and finish her education is this. Studies repeatedly show that girls who experience multiple disadvantages, such as low family income, living in remote or underserved areas, having any kind of disability, or being a member of a minority ethnolinguistic group, lag behind the most in terms of access to and completion of education.

Violence

Another significant barrier to females' access to or completion of school is violence. The majority of girls go significant distances to school and live in isolated areas, increasing their vulnerability to sexual assault and abuse. According to the most recent statistics, 60 million girls worldwide experience sexual assault each year either on the route to or while at school. Their overall wellbeing, including their physical and mental health, are frequently severely affected, which has negative effects on attendance and dropout rates.

Early Marriage

Girls are far more likely to be forced to leave school due to early marriage. Additionally, they are more likely to have children at an early age and are subjected to higher levels of violence from their partners, all of which have a detrimental effect on their own and their children's health. Not to mention the consequences of their lack of education and their capacity to make a respectable living. A recent study found that every day, more than 41,000 girls under the age of 18 get married. Eliminating this practise would raise the expected educational level of women and, consequently, their prospective wages. Every year, an estimated 246 million children are subjected to abuse in and around schools; for this reason, it is essential to put an end to gender-based violence in schools.

Actions to increase women's education: It should go without saying that the aforementioned goals can only be met by first and foremost ensuring that women receive high-quality education. When this is accomplished, women will have the knowledge, abilities, attitudes, and other potentials necessary for full involvement in national development.

The following goals are set forward to advance women's education:

1. Enable women to enhance the diet and health of their families.
2. Improve women's productivity so that their families can live better.
3. Provide women with access to necessary technologies and cooperative management

4. Boost the social and cultural prominence of women.
5. Make it possible for women to carry out their tasks more skilfully
6. Assist women in overcoming their own anxieties and emotions of worthlessness or inferiority
7. Promote the holistic development of women, including their mental, social, physical, psychological, religious, and economic well-being.

Conclusion:

In order to achieve social justice and build an inclusive society free from inequality, education is essential. Regardless of their socioeconomic situation, caste, creed, or origin, every Indian child must have the chance to receive a high-quality education. It is important to remember that how people feel about women's education will explain a lot about how much they want their country to advance. As is said, educating a woman is like educating the entire society. Education is regarded as a crucial tool for the empowerment of women. It alters their way of life, raises their social status, increases their work prospects, and makes it easier for them to participate in public life. Even though there has been significant improvement in literacy and education, the general structure is still not advantageous to women.

India is working hard to ensure that women have access to high-quality education everywhere in the nation. It is clear that education is essential for social equality, scientific progress, economic growth, and cultural preservation. India will have the largest population in the world in ten years. The actions we take in the field of education now will have an effect on the future of billions of Indians. The Indian government, realising the seriousness of the problem, developed the new National Education Policy, which intends to significantly enhance the educational ecosystem and raise women's literacy rates throughout the nation.

References:

1. Dominic B., Jothi C.A. (2012). Education- A tool of Women Empowerment: Historical study based on Kerala society. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 2(4), 2250-3153.
2. <http://www.novapdf.com>
3. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/271335/literacy-rate-in-india>
4. Nisha Nair. (2010). Women's education in India: A situational analysis. *IMJ*, 1(4), 100-114.
5. Ramachandran V. *Girls and women education: Policies and implementation mechanisms; case study: India*. Bangkok: UNESCO. Principal Regional Office for Asia and the Pacific, 1998.
6. Bhat R.A. (2015). Role of Education in the Empowerment of Women in India. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(10), 188-191

7. <https://www.careindia.org/resources/importance-of-girl-education/>
8. <https://yourstory.com/mystory/why-is-education-important-for-women-fiqb8h1ie>
9. <https://assignmentpoint.com/importance-women-education/>